

The ICON-ParFlow Coupling: Integrating a Continental-Scale Hydrological Model into a Global Atmospheric Model

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Abstract

In Earth system models, three-dimensional prognostic groundwater flow and transport is currently missing at the global scale. In order to prepare Earth system models for kilometer-scale simulations with integrated continental hydrology, the ParFlow hydrological model has been coupled to the land model of the ICON modeling framework. Global simulations of atmosphere and land were conducted with a two-way coupling between ParFlow and the soil hydrological scheme of ICON-Land over the pan-European region. In this first configuration, ParFlow and ICON-Land exchange surface moisture fluxes and soil water. The extended summer months of five consecutive years were simulated. The soil water variability is found to be reduced in the deeper soil layers as ParFlow resolves shallow aquifers. In contrast, soil water variability near the surface increases both spatially and temporally. In ParFlow, surface water is simulated in an integrated fashion leading to a more physical lateral redistribution of moisture. Correlations with surface latent heat flux and precipitation show that this results in regionally stronger land-atmosphere coupling. This contributes to a more pronounced and also more realistic soil water deficit in Europe at the end of summer. In addition, the lateral flow of near-surface groundwater, which is intrinsically linked to the formation of river networks, influences the evolution of the atmospheric boundary layer.

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10 **Key Points:**

- 11 • The ICON-ParFlow coupling allows global-scale coupled simulations between at-
12 mosphere, land, and subsurface hydrology
- 13 • Resolved surface water and three-dimensional groundwater flow lead to differences
14 in the evolution of soil water content
- 15 • Due to partly increased land-atmosphere coupling, a stronger decline in soil wa-
16 ter can be observed in parts of Europe over the summer

Abstract

In Earth system models, three-dimensional prognostic groundwater flow and transport is currently missing at the global scale. In order to prepare Earth system models for kilometer-scale simulations with integrated continental hydrology, the ParFlow hydrological model has been coupled to the land model of the ICON modeling framework. Global simulations of atmosphere and land were conducted with a two-way coupling between ParFlow and the soil hydrological scheme of ICON-Land over the pan-European region. In this first configuration, ParFlow and ICON-Land exchange surface moisture fluxes and soil water. The extended summer months of five consecutive years were simulated. The soil water variability is found to be reduced in the deeper soil layers as ParFlow resolves shallow aquifers. In contrast, soil water variability near the surface increases both spatially and temporally. In ParFlow, surface water is simulated in an integrated fashion leading to a more physical lateral redistribution of moisture. Correlations with surface latent heat flux and precipitation show that this results in regionally stronger land-atmosphere coupling. This contributes to a more pronounced and also more realistic soil water deficit in Central Europe at the end of summer. In addition, the lateral flow of near-surface groundwater, which is intrinsically linked to the formation of river networks, influences the evolution of the atmospheric boundary layer.

Plain Language Summary

In most global weather and climate models, the representation of surface and groundwater is very simplified. We have coupled a hydrological model (ParFlow) to the land component of an Earth system model (ICON with ICON-Land). In ParFlow, surface streamflow evolves based on physical principles according to topography, sustaining a consistent water table depth. The coupling allows global coupled simulations between atmosphere, land, and subsurface hydrology without the need for external boundary data. In the simulations presented here, while ICON and ICON-Land run globally, the ParFlow coverage is limited to the pan-European region and the resolution is relatively coarse. In the coupled simulations, soil moisture variability decreases in the deeper soil layers while temporal and spatial variability increase in the upper layers. This is because river valleys remain wet and connected to the groundwater table while water divides are more susceptible to drying. Partly, this is related to stronger land-atmosphere coupling. Lateral groundwater flow in particular can be shown to have a significant influence on the evolution of the atmosphere. Compared to reference simulations, the drop in soil moisture over the summer months is stronger, which is more realistic for the years considered in this study.

1 Introduction

Closing the hydrological cycle from the continents to the oceans is an integral part of Earth system modeling. From the perspective of atmospheric modeling, continental land masses represent a sink for moisture as annual precipitation typically exceeds evapotranspiration. Thus, surface water runoff and subsurface drainage need to be modeled by land surface schemes in order to close the terrestrial water budget in climate simulations. By computing the surface energy balance and exchange fluxes of heat and mass, land surface schemes directly influence the evolution of the atmospheric boundary layer. Also, studies have shown that land surface fluxes can be strongly coupled to groundwater-table processes (Kollet & Maxwell, 2008; Maxwell & Kollet, 2008; Taylor et al., 2013; Fan, 2015; Rahman et al., 2015; Keune et al., 2016). This demonstrates the need for integrated hydrological models for feedback modeling and motivated the integration of prognostic, variably saturated groundwater models solving the three-dimensional Richards equation into large-scale climate simulations. An example is the Terrestrial Systems Modeling Platform (TSMP, Shrestha et al., 2014; Gasper et al., 2014) consisting of the at-

67 atmospheric model COSMO, the Community Land Model (CLM), and the surface-subsurface
 68 model ParFlow (Kollet & Maxwell, 2006; Maxwell, 2013). ParFlow is a fully integrated,
 69 physics-based model that simulates surface and variably saturated subsurface flow as a
 70 continuum. Thus, in the simulations, rivers and groundwater flow are naturally evol-
 71 ving depending on topography, hydrological parameters, and two-way feedbacks with land-
 72 surface fluxes and ambient atmospheric conditions. With TSMP, this has been shown
 73 at the regional scale over the European CORDEX domain at 12.5 km (Keune et al., 2016;
 74 Poshyvailo-Strube et al., 2024) and 3 km resolution (Naz et al., 2023). While ground-
 75 water to top-of-atmosphere modeling has arrived at the continental scale solving the re-
 76 gional boundary value problem, global-scale hydrological models are still rather concep-
 77 tual or focus on other aspects such as flood hazard and water availability (Do et al., 2020;
 78 Stacke & Hagemann, 2021). Uncertainty in these models is large because of major sim-
 79 plifying assumptions and compartmentalization in simulating the water continuum (Barlage
 80 et al., 2021; Reinecke et al., 2024).

81 The current limitations in global Earth system and hydrological models require ad-
 82 ditional physics and model improvements as the community moves towards kilometer-
 83 scale resolution (Stevens et al., 2019; Hohenegger et al., 2023). The ICON Earth system
 84 model (ICON-ESM) is a modeling framework consisting of an atmosphere model (ICON-
 85 A), an ocean model (ICON-O) built on the same model infrastructure, a land model (ICON-
 86 Land), and other model components. Generally, the ICON model framework is based
 87 on an unstructured, icosahedral grid (Giorgetta et al., 2018; Jungclaus et al., 2022). ICON-
 88 A and ICON-O as well as other model components are coupled via the YAC coupling
 89 software (Yet Another Coupler, Hanke et al., 2016). ICON-Land simulates land processes
 90 and the terrestrial carbon cycle using the Jena Scheme for Biosphere-Atmosphere Cou-
 91 pling in Hamburg JSBACHv4, which is based off the JSBACHv3 land model (Reick et
 92 al., 2021). JSBACHv4 features a tile approach and an object-oriented programming style.
 93 It includes a five-layer snow scheme and the functionality of soil water phase changes (Ekici
 94 et al., 2014; de Vrese et al., 2021). The soil scheme uses five soil layers ranging 9.8 m be-
 95 low the surface with increasing thickness towards the lower boundary. Surface runoff and
 96 subsurface drainage from the ICON grid cells are directed to the ocean via a hydrologic
 97 discharge model (Hagemann & Dümenil, 1997). ICON has been tested for climate sim-
 98 ulations and implemented on various high-performance computing (HPC) systems and
 99 architectures (Crueger et al., 2018; Giorgetta et al., 2022).

100 Generally, changes in soil water content will have a systematic influence on surface
 101 temperature, latent heat flux, and evaporation (Seneviratne et al., 2006; Keune et al.,
 102 2016; Poshyvailo-Strube et al., 2024). Relations between variables can be illustrated with
 103 the help of feedback cycles based on the exchange of heat and mass between land sur-
 104 face and atmosphere (Seneviratne et al., 2010; Müller et al., 2021; Hartick et al., 2022;
 105 Zhang et al., 2024). Thus, land-atmosphere coupling can be understood as a complete
 106 feedback loop including the atmospheric response to dynamics in surface and subsurface
 107 hydrology. Dirmeyer (2011), for instance, defines a terrestrial branch where soil mois-
 108 ture changes drive surface flux variability. It can be depicted via the correlation between
 109 soil moisture and latent heat flux. An atmospheric branch, on the other hand, identi-
 110 fies whether changes in latent heat flux are correlated with precipitation (Dirmeyer et
 111 al., 2014). This way, land-atmosphere coupling is found to be strong in regions where
 112 both segments of the coupling are strong. In meteorological extremes such as heat waves,
 113 soil moisture is crucial for the development of extreme temperature anomalies (Schumacher
 114 et al., 2019; Stegehuis et al., 2021). Even down to single convective precipitation events,
 115 a connection can be drawn between groundwater-table dynamics and atmospheric pro-
 116 cesses (Rahman et al., 2015). In a wider perspective, the soil moisture-temperature feed-
 117 back and the feedback on precipitation can be expected to intensify the hydrological cy-
 118 cle in the presence of climate change (Huntington, 2006).

119 In this study, a coupling between the ParFlow hydrological model and ICON-Land
 120 is proposed. This is motivated by ParFlow’s more physics-based approach to surface and
 121 subsurface flow compared to the JSBACH hydrological scheme, which features a single-
 122 column soil water scheme in combination with parameterized drainage and discharge.
 123 With increasing horizontal grid resolution towards convection-permitting resolution in
 124 global climate modeling, the lateral flow component of surface and subsurface water can
 125 be expected to become more important (Barlage et al., 2021). Furthermore, a param-
 126 eterized network of river basins will not properly scale with grid resolution, meaning that
 127 it does not naturally refine into a more detailed network of streams and creeks even if
 128 high-resolution elevation data is provided. Thus, integrating ParFlow with ICON-Land
 129 can be expected to produce more realistic results when moving to kilometer-scale res-
 130 olution. In addition, deeper flow systems can be simulated in ParFlow. Thus, a wider
 131 range of time scales and subsurface-land surface interactions can be resolved from ground-
 132 water recharge to discharge zones, i.e., river corridors. Generally, added value is created
 133 by the lateral redistribution of surface and subsurface water, streamflow-aquifer inter-
 134 actions linked to convergence zones and the evolution of river networks, hillslope pro-
 135 cesses, and possible infiltration or saturation excess.

136 Coupling ParFlow with an Earth system model or general circulation model (GCM)
 137 instead of a regional climate model (RCM) has the advantage that no atmospheric bound-
 138 ary conditions are needed to drive the model system. By relaxing this boundary-value
 139 problem, which is inherent in all RCM studies, potential impacts of groundwater dynam-
 140 ics on the large-scale circulation can be modeled for the first time. Overall, this study
 141 is a proof-of-concept and a first evaluation of the ICON-ParFlow coupling. With that,
 142 it features a relatively coarse horizontal resolution of 20 km. Although the analysis of
 143 land-atmosphere feedback cycles has already been applied to coupled simulations within
 144 the scope of TSMP (Keune et al., 2016; Furusho-Percot et al., 2022), our study focuses
 145 on the changed characteristics of surface and subsurface hydrology in coupled ICON-ParFlow
 146 simulations compared to the ICON-Land soil hydrology scheme, as well as the effect of
 147 the additional model capabilities introduced by the ParFlow coupling, such as resolved
 148 surface flow and three-dimensional subsurface flow.

149 The article is structured as follows: In the next section, ICON, ICON-Land, and
 150 ParFlow are first briefly introduced. In Section 2.2, the coupling is described in detail.
 151 Section 2.3 presents the experimental setup. The simulation results are analyzed and dis-
 152 cussed in Section 3 followed by a comparison to reanalysis data in Section 4. Conclu-
 153 sive remarks are given in Section 5.

154 2 Methods

155 In the following, the modeling systems, coupling strategy, and experimental design
 156 of the nested ParFlow in global ICON simulations are described. Focus is placed on the
 157 key concepts that distinguish the proposed approach from the current integration of ParFlow
 158 with regional climate simulations, and the simplifying assumptions that are applied in
 159 the implementation.

160 2.1 Modeling System

161 2.1.1 *ICON Atmosphere and Land*

162 The ICON model in its Sapphire configuration is a state-of-the-art Earth system
 163 model explicitly resolving the flow of energy and mass on grid spacings around and be-
 164 low 10 km. For the atmosphere, the non-hydrostatic set of equations is solved on an icosahedral-
 165 triangular grid with the possibility to place limited-area nests. In the vertical, a terrain-
 166 following sigma z coordinate is used applying Rayleigh damping in the top layers. Ra-
 167 diation is modeled by the Radiative Transfer for Energetics RRTMG scheme. For the

168 microphysical processes, a one-moment scheme is used. Subgrid-scale turbulence is pa-
 169 rameterized by a 3D Smagorinsky-style scheme that is similar to turbulence schemes used
 170 in large-eddy simulations. Atmospheric processes that can principally be resolved by the
 171 governing equations such as shallow convection, subgrid-scale cloud cover, and orographic
 172 drag are not parameterized (Hohenegger et al., 2023).

173 ICON-Land employs the land model JSBACHv4, which follows a tile approach where
 174 a land cell can be subdivided into fractions of vegetated land, lake, or glacier. Latent and
 175 sensible heat fluxes are computed from similarity theory. Apart from that, ICON-Land
 176 provides albedo, surface roughness, and other parameters to the ICON model system.
 177 A multi-layer soil hydrology scheme calculates the soil water storage. It allows for freez-
 178 ing and melting of water while a multi-layer snow scheme addresses snow and ice on the
 179 land surface. Other processes more related to biogeochemistry are leaf phenology, dy-
 180 namical vegetation, photosynthesis, and carbon cycles, as well as natural and anthro-
 181 pogenic changes in land cover. In this study, however, a simplified version of ICON-Land
 182 is used simulating only the physical land processes. Leaf phenology, e.g., is prescribed
 183 by a monthly climatology.

184 **2.1.2 ParFlow**

185 The ParFlow hydrological model simulates variably saturated groundwater flow in
 186 combination with two-dimensional overland flow. A free-surface upper boundary con-
 187 dition is applied in order to model surface and subsurface water in a continuum approach
 188 (Kollet & Maxwell, 2006). For the subsurface, it solves the mixed form of the 3D Richards
 189 equation. The surface runoff is calculated by a kinematic wave equation. The Richards
 190 equation is discretized using a cell-centered finite difference scheme and solved by a time-
 191 implicit Eulerian scheme using a Newton-Krylov non-linear method. Head potential and
 192 water saturation are computed as prognostic variables. A terrain-following grid trans-
 193 formation with a variable vertical discretization is used for this study (Maxwell, 2013).
 194 ParFlow is fully parallelized, performance portable, and has been demonstrated to scale
 195 efficiently to a large number of parallel tasks (Kollet et al., 2010; Hokkanen et al., 2021).
 196 For further details regarding the ParFlow modeling system, the reader is referred to the
 197 aforementioned publications.

198 **2.2 Coupling Strategy and Implementation**

199 Technically, the coupling between ICON-Land and ParFlow is achieved by the YAC
 200 coupler (Hanke et al., 2016). YAC is able to interpolate between different model grids
 201 as ParFlow is restricted to a Cartesian grid. Also, different temporal resolutions are possi-
 202 ble and different interpolation methods are available. Generally, the coupling involves
 203 sending the fluxes from precipitation, melting, etc., as well as the evapotranspiration to
 204 ParFlow while receiving an updated field of the soil water content in return based on three-
 205 dimensional, variably saturated groundwater and surface water flow. Details are provided
 206 in the following section. Note that, in its current stage, the coupling does not replace
 207 the existing ICON-Land hydrology in terms of model infrastructure. Due to consider-
 208 able differences in the design of both ParFlow and the ICON-Land hydrological scheme,
 209 a less strict coupling approach, where the soil water content is regularly updated by the
 210 values from ParFlow, was found to be more practical. Although this requires certain sim-
 211 plifications, which are described below, the main feedbacks between both models are in-
 212 cluded leading to results that can be analyzed.

213 **2.2.1 Exchanged Variables**

214 In the presented version of the ICON-ParFlow coupling, ParFlow accounts only for
 215 liquid water. No snow or soil ice is considered. Thus, only the soil water content and the
 216 net water flux (P-ET) are exchanged between ICON-Land and ParFlow. With that, the

217 exchange is limited to mass so that the energy budget in ICON-Land is affected solely
 218 via the coupling of the water and energy cycles. While ParFlow calculates the ground-
 219 water potential as a prognostic variable in terms of pressure head, this variable is not
 220 passed as the ICON-Land parameterizations, which were designed for global climate sim-
 221 ulations, rely on the soil water content (measured in m water equivalent). This variable
 222 is calculated prior to the exchange from ParFlow’s saturation via the porosity and the
 223 soil layer thickness. The net water flux is received by ParFlow as a volumetric flux (unit
 224 h^{-1}) per area and unit depth of the subsurface. All positive contributions to the net wa-
 225 ter flux including precipitation reaching the ground, dew, and melt water are grouped
 226 into one variable before ICON-Land does the runoff/infiltration partitioning. This also
 227 includes contributions from lake or glacier tiles originating from precipitation or thaw-
 228 ing that would otherwise directly go into ICON-Land runoff. In a last step, negative con-
 229 tributions from evaporation and transpiration are added to arrive at the aforementioned
 230 net water flux (P-ET). Here, the reduction by transpiration is distributed uniformly along
 231 the vertical root zone. This makes the net water flux from ICON-Land to ParFlow a three-
 232 dimensional exchange variable.

233 As ICON-Land actually allows for soil water freezing and the formation of soil ice,
 234 it is required that the ParFlow coupling does not generate latent heat by introducing liq-
 235 uid water into an actually frozen soil layer. As an ad-hoc solution, this is done by lim-
 236 iting the soil water content received from ParFlow to the field capacity of liquid water
 237 in ICON-Land. The resulting difference in soil water content between ICON-Land and
 238 ParFlow can be tracked and monitored in the model output. In ICON-Land, the field
 239 capacity of liquid water is continuously updated according to the current amount of soil
 240 ice. A soil volume is regarded fully saturated as soon as the soil water content reaches
 241 the field capacity. Any excess water is added to a drainage variable and subsequently
 242 removed from the soil column. In case of rivers, actual surface water flow is only rep-
 243 resented in ParFlow while ICON-Land accounts for a fully saturated soil volume that
 244 is still able to evaporate water at the thermodynamic limit given by the local ambient
 245 atmospheric conditions.

246 **2.2.2 Horizontal Grid Matching**

247 YAC has been designed to interpolate between different grids commonly used in
 248 Earth system modeling. The ICON grid is already defined as an unstructured grid within
 249 the ICON coupling functionality. The ParFlow setup featuring the European CORDEX
 250 domain is based on a regular longitude-latitude grid with a rotated pole (-162.0° lon-
 251 gitudinal, 39.25° latitudinal) leading to a point of origin centered over Europe. This min-
 252 imizes the grid error when using ParFlow’s rectangular computational grid to represent
 253 a continental-scale area on the globe. For the coupling definition in the ParFlow YAC
 254 interface, the back-rotated coordinates of the cell centers and vertices of the ParFlow grid
 255 are used to define a two-dimensional curvilinear grid that YAC then uses for the hor-
 256 izontal interpolation. By default, YAC only interpolates between the overlapping areas
 257 of the source and the target grid. Thus, no additional information needs to be defined
 258 in order to mask areas outside the ParFlow coverage. Second-order conservative inter-
 259 polation is used for the soil water content as well as the net water flux from ICON-Land
 260 to ParFlow. Along the perimeter of the ParFlow domain, ICON cells only partially cov-
 261 ered by the ParFlow grid receive a value based on fractional-area normalization. In con-
 262 trast to destination-area normalization, this method produces reasonable values for soil
 263 water content but does not ensure local conservation. However, considering the relatively
 264 short simulation time of only a few months, this effect was neglected here.

265 **2.2.3 Vertical Grid Matching**

266 YAC does not allow interpolation between different vertical grids to account for the
 267 different vertical spacing in ParFlow and ICON-Land. However, exchanging a stack (‘col-

lection size') of two-dimensional fields of the same variable is possible. The vertical grid spacing and the depth of the domain differs considerably between ICON-Land and ParFlow. ParFlow in the current European CORDEX setup covers 15 vertical layers down to 60 m below the land surface. The vertical spacing increases from 2 cm in the top layer up to 18 m in the two deepest layers. In ICON-Land, the topmost layer has a thickness of 6.5 cm increasing to 5.7 m at a maximum depth of 9.8 m. Data is only exchanged along the overlapping part of the subsurface. A first-order conservative interpolation routine in the ParFlow-YAC interface remaps the exchanged variables between the ICON-Land and the ParFlow vertical grids. In a first-order conservative interpolation, the value for each target layer is computed as a weighted sum of source-layer values, with the contribution of one source layer being proportional to the fraction of the target layer covered by the source layer.

2.2.4 Time Stepping

In the applied setup, ICON uses a constant time step of 40 s. Due to the dynamics of the simulated hydrological processes and the implicit time-stepping method used, the time step in ParFlow is larger, currently 30 min. While YAC allows for a coupling time step differing from each model time step, both need to be integer multiples. By design, the ICON-Land processes are called at every atmospheric time step. Thus, the ParFlow time step would need to be reduced to the ICON time step in order to continuously update the soil water content affecting the performance. As a compromise, both the ParFlow time step and the coupling interval was set to 6 min. Consequently, the soil water content is updated in ICON-Land every ninth time step. At all other time steps, the default ICON-Land soil water scheme is applied. The water available for runoff or infiltration as well as the amount of evapotranspiration sent to ParFlow is accumulated over the coupling interval ensuring that the full amount of liquid water is exchanged between ParFlow and ICON-Land.

2.3 Experimental Setup

The simulations are set up with ICON and ICON-Land at the global scale. The ParFlow domain is nested into global ICON over the pan-European area as a specific region of interest. Here, ParFlow is coupled into the global simulations via ICON-Land as described above. Throughout the remaining part of the land mass, the default ICON-Land soil water scheme is used. However, land-atmosphere interactions occurring regionally over Europe, where the land surface is coupled to groundwater dynamics, potentially influence large-scale dynamics beyond the coupling region.

For the ParFlow component model, the official EUR-11 grid of the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX, Gutowski Jr et al., 2016) at 0.11° horizontal resolution is used. For the 15 subsurface layers down to 60 m depth, the soil hydraulic properties and hydrological parameters need to be specified. The soil texture data determining the hydraulic conductivity based on sand and clay percentages are derived from the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) database (Batjes, 1997). Further information about the underlying bedrock are based on the BGR International Hydrogeological Map of Europe (Duscher et al., 2015). Because TSMP simulations exist for this model domain, ParFlow can be initialized at a specific point in time using the subsurface pressure data from the continuous ERA5-driven COSMO-CLM-ParFlow coupled simulation on the European CORDEX domain (Furusho-Percot et al., 2019). This multi-decadal simulation guarantees a spun-up groundwater configuration.

For ICON, the setup is based on the QUBICC configuration, which also includes certain simplifications in ICON-Land. Details can be found in Giorgetta et al. (2022). The horizontal resolution is R2B7 (approximately 20 km). This relatively coarse resolution was used as spun-up groundwater configurations for ParFlow are readily available at a resolution of 12.5 km and the next higher ICON resolution would be roughly 10 km

Figure 1. Differences in total soil water storage and latent heat flux between ICON-PFL and the ICON-REF averaged over the extended summer period of 2004.

318 (R2B8). In the vertical, the QUBICC configuration extends up to the upper stratosphere.
 319 This has been left unchanged due to the importance of stratospheric processes for sea-
 320 sonal simulations (Domeisen et al., 2020).

321 The simulations are carried out without dynamic ocean coupling; therefore, quan-
 322 tities such as sea surface temperature and sea-ice cover are prescribed based on monthly
 323 climatological data. The atmosphere in ICON as well as some basic land surface vari-
 324 ables in ICON-Land such as skin and soil temperature, soil moisture, and snow cover are
 325 initialized from IFS analysis data. Starting on March 15, six months of the years 2002
 326 to 2006 are simulated in order to cover the summer season of each year until end of Septem-
 327 ber. Note that both the ICON reference and the ICON-ParFlow simulations are running
 328 freely after initialization. Model results are compared to stand-alone ICON simulations
 329 serving as a reference.

330 3 Simulation Analysis

331 3.1 Description of the Coupled Simulation

332 In the following, the results of the coupled ICON-ParFlow simulation (ICON-PFL)
 333 are analyzed and compared to a stand-alone ICON reference simulation (ICON-REF).
 334 Averaged differences between the two 2004 simulations in total soil water storage and
 335 surface latent heat flux are shown in Figure 1. The averaging period extends over the
 336 extended summer months from beginning of May to end of September. Overall, large
 337 areas turn out to be slightly wetter while some regions end up considerably dryer in the
 338 simulation with ParFlow. ICON-Land and ParFlow treat subsurface and surface water
 339 flow in fundamentally different ways. ICON-Land applies a 1D implementation of the
 340 Richards equation intended for coarser grid resolutions in global climate simulations. In
 341 contrast, ParFlow is based on the partial differential equations for saturation and ground-
 342 water pressure. Solving the Richards equation in 3D, and using different parameter sets,
 343 leads to the generation of shallow aquifers with a free water table connected to surface
 344 water, surface-water aquifer interactions in river valley convergence zones, and lateral
 345 redistribution of surface and subsurface water. In ICON-PFL, this leads to different dis-
 346 tributions of soil moisture and latent heat flux over large regions. Differences in the
 347 latent heat flux are very heterogeneous with river basins sticking out as positive deviations,
 348 e.g., north of the Black Sea.

Figure 2. Relative change in soil water content in the upper soil layers from beginning to end of summer (JJA) averaged over an ensemble of the years 2002 to 2006.

3.2 Changes in Soil Water Distribution

To assess the evolution of soil water storage both in ICON-REF and in ICON-PFL relative to the different initial conditions, the relative change in soil water content over the summer season (JJA) is presented in Figure 2. As it is most relevant for the interaction with the atmosphere, only the upper 30 cm are considered. We chose the summer months when snow and ice processes are secondary in most parts of Europe, apart from high latitudes and mountainous areas. In order to arrive at robust results, a mean was computed over the multi-year ensemble (2002 to 2006). The results show that the soil water storage in ICON-PFL is subject to a stronger decrease over the course of several months. Compared to the uncoupled ICON-REF simulations, the upper soil layers in most parts of Europe are dryer at the end of the summer while wetter soils can be observed along the North Atlantic and the Arctic Coast. Generally, there is a continuous groundwater table on the continent, which is strongly connected to land-surface processes in case of relatively shallow water tables. As shallow water tables are well represented in ParFlow, we argue that, on average, the ICON-PFL simulations (Figure 2b) are more realistic. In particular, a stronger change in soil water content indicates that, with the ParFlow coupling, the land surface reacts more sensitively to the atmosphere resulting in stronger land-atmosphere coupling. More details on land-atmosphere interaction will be provided in Section 3.4. A comparison of the results shown here with ERA5 reanalysis data will be presented in Section 4.

3.3 Soil Water Variability

Due to different parameter sets in ParFlow and ICON-Land and a different subsurface configuration at the time of initialization, it is not meaningful to compare ICON-REF and ICON-PFL simulations in terms of absolute quantities such as accumulated precipitation or daily maximum temperature. Thus, instead of the actual soil water distribution, the temporal soil water variability was found to be more insightful. The temporal variability of the soil water content is depicted in Figure 3 as the standard deviation over the extended summer season (May to September) of 2004. We distinguish between the upper (0 - 30 cm) and the deeper soil layers (0.3 - 10 m) both for ICON-REF and ICON-PFL. The standard deviation is based on weekly averages of the soil water content in order to smooth out short-term changes related to single precipitation events. The data has been detrended in order to compensate for the seasonal change in soil water distribution. Figure 3a and b show that the soil water storage in the lower layers is temporally less variable in the coupled simulation due to resolved shallow groundwater,

Figure 3. Temporal variability (detrended) of the soil water content in ICON-REF and ICON-PFL in the upper soil layers (a and b) as well as the deeper soil layers (c and d). The variability is measured by the standard deviation over the extended summer period of 2004 based on weekly averages. The data has been detrended in order to compensate for the seasonal change. The standard deviation is normalized by the mean soil water content.

383 especially in southern and southeast Europe. In fact, average weekly fluctuations of 10 %
 384 or more in the deeper layers (Figure 3a) cannot be considered realistic in larger areas,
 385 especially since the averaging period extends over five months. An area where the soil
 386 water content of the deeper soil is still highly variable even in the ICON-PFL simula-
 387 tion (Figure 3b) is along the Arctic Ocean. However, the exchange of liquid water be-
 388 tween ICON-Land and ParFlow is expected to be strongly limited in that region because
 389 of the high percentage of frozen water in the soil. Another characteristic of the ICON-
 390 PFL simulation is that the soil water content is considerably less variable in the deeper
 391 soil than in the upper layers (Figure 3b and d). While this is in contrast to the ICON-
 392 REF simulation (a and c), it can be considered more realistic because of the balancing
 393 influence of groundwater aquifers. At the same time, when comparing the variability in
 394 the upper layers (c and d), the ICON-PFL simulation shows partly higher values. Hor-
 395 izontally, the standard deviation of the soil water content is also more uneven. This in-
 396 creased heterogeneity is determined by river basins with constantly low soil water vari-
 397 ability within areas of frequent wetting and drying during the summer months. Thus,
 398 the higher soil water variability near the surface in the ICON-PFL simulation will be highly
 399 influenced by surface runoff and the depth of the groundwater table below the surface,
 400 which are both determined by topography. Consequently, differences between ICON-REF
 401 and ICON-PFL are less likely to be caused only by different hydrological parameters but
 402 also by structural model differences.

403 While soil water variability near the surface influences land-atmosphere coupling,
 404 the deeper soil water will less strongly affect land surface fluxes although it can do so
 405 to some extent via capillary rise. Instead, the main contributor to the reduced soil wa-
 406 ter variability in the deeper layers in ICON-PFL is probably the much deeper subsur-
 407 face in ParFlow so that the soil water storage above 10 m is much less affected by any
 408 lower boundary condition. Another factor influencing soil water variability may be the
 409 numerical implementation of the ICON-Land soil water scheme using the saturation-based
 410 form of the Richards equation. In the implementation, soil moisture exceeding the field
 411 capacity is either removed from the soil column into drainage or the hydraulic conduc-
 412 tivity, which is reaching its maximum value at field capacity, allows a maximum amount
 413 of soil water to percolate into bottom drainage. In both cases, an aquifer with a shal-
 414 low groundwater table and lateral flow cannot be approximated.

415 **3.4 Impact on Land-Atmosphere Coupling**

416 Numerous studies have shown that regional climate variability is influenced by in-
 417 teractions between the atmosphere and the land surface. Generally, land-atmosphere cou-
 418 pling can help explain the evolution of weather and climate across various spatial and
 419 temporal scales (Santanello Jr et al., 2018). For instance, land-atmosphere coupling con-
 420 siderably influences the water cycle via impacts on clouds and precipitation (Seneviratne
 421 et al., 2006, 2010; Jeon et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024) and is found to correlate with
 422 the onset and intensity of heat waves (Miralles et al., 2019; Schumacher et al., 2019; Dirmeyer
 423 et al., 2021) or changes in regional climate regimes (Berg et al., 2017; Findell et al., 2019;
 424 Schwitalla et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). Several metrics have been proposed to an-
 425alyze land-atmosphere interactions (Santanello Jr et al., 2018). Typically, statistical cor-
 426 relations are used to quantify the response of an atmospheric variable to an anomaly in
 427 the state of the land surface and vice versa. Thus, land-atmosphere coupling is pronounced
 428 in regions where the state of the atmosphere is sensitive to variations in land-surface prop-
 429 erties and where there is a high temporal variability in the state of the land surface (Koster
 430 et al., 2004; Guo et al., 2006; Dirmeyer, 2011). In terms of soil moisture and evapora-
 431 tion, this leads to the formation of two distinct regimes (Seneviratne et al., 2010). In re-
 432 gions where soil moisture is the limiting factor, any variation in soil moisture strongly
 433 corresponds to a variation in evaporation. In combination with an increase in precipi-
 434 tation linked to an increase in evaporation, this leads to strong land-atmosphere coupling,
 435 i.e., variations in moisture correlate with precipitation. In an area of abundant soil mois-

Figure 4. Evaluation of the land-atmosphere coupling using two-legged metrics consisting of the contributions from the land surface (a and b), the atmosphere (c and d), and the total coupling strength (e and f) over the extended summer period of 2004 based on weekly averages. The standard deviation is normalized by the temporal mean.

436 ture, an energy-limited regime emerges indicating weak land-atmosphere coupling. In
 437 order to better represent the feedback cycle, a two-legged index has been proposed, di-
 438 viding the land-atmosphere interaction chain into a land and an atmosphere leg (Dirmeyer,
 439 2011; Dirmeyer et al., 2014). Typically, the land leg includes the correlation between soil
 440 moisture and the surface fluxes of heat, moisture, or momentum. The atmosphere leg
 441 can be constructed as a combination of latent or sensible heat flux and the accumulated
 442 precipitation or the growth of the planetary boundary layer, respectively. Here, the fol-
 443 lowing metrics for the land leg \mathcal{L} , the atmosphere leg \mathcal{A} , and the total linkage \mathcal{T} are cho-
 444 sen similarly to Yin et al. (2023):

- 445 • Land leg: $\mathcal{L} = \rho(\theta, LE) \cdot \sigma_{LE}$
- 446 • Atmosphere leg: $\mathcal{A} = \rho(LE, Pr) \cdot \sigma_{Pr}$
- 447 • Total coupling: $\mathcal{T} = \rho(\theta, LE) \cdot \rho(LE, Pr) \cdot \sigma_{Pr}$

448 They feature the soil water content of the upper soil layers (0 - 30 cm) θ , the sur-
 449 face latent heat flux LE, and the accumulated precipitation Pr while ρ is the Pearson
 450 correlation coefficient and σ is the standard deviation. Exemplarily, this analysis was per-
 451 formed for the extended summer season of 2004. Figure 4e and f show that, in general,
 452 the land-atmosphere coupling strength is slightly increased in the ICON-PFL simula-
 453 tion over large parts of Central and Eastern Europe. This is mainly due to a strongly
 454 positive correlation between soil moisture and latent heat flux compared to a much weaker
 455 or partly negative correlation in the ICON-REF simulation (Figure 4a and b). The posi-
 456 tive correlation over eastern Europe in ICON-PFL originates either from an upper soil
 457 layer that is more prone to frequent wetting and drying due to differences in infiltration
 458 and runoff so that the feedback cycle enters the moisture-limited regime more often, or
 459 a permanently dryer upper soil layer so that the feedback cycle is more likely to remain
 460 in that regime. Thereby, a permanently dryer upper soil layer may also be a consequence
 461 of stronger land-atmosphere coupling. The correlation between latent heat flux and pre-
 462 cipitation, which is part of the atmosphere leg, shows higher magnitudes as well (Fig-
 463 ure 4c and d). This indicates a more heterogeneous distribution of latent heat flux and
 464 precipitation, which is related to river networks and topography, among other influenc-
 465 ing factors. This means that the moisture supply coming from precipitation is horizon-
 466 tally redistributed by surface flow and near-surface groundwater flow, thus, in some re-
 467 gions, an increase in precipitation leads to an increase in surface latent heat flux, which,
 468 one may speculate, is then also more likely to induce new precipitation. Generally, the
 469 correlation between latent heat flux and precipitation increases from northwest to south-
 470 east with the climate becoming dryer and more continental.

471 3.5 Role of Lateral Groundwater Flow

One key difference of the ICON-Land hydrological scheme compared to ParFlow
 is the lack of resolved lateral flow. Figure 1b demonstrates that surface water develop-
 ing into a river network directly corresponds to changes in the surface energy fluxes. In
 general, this increases spatial heterogeneity due to horizontal soil moisture differences
 between hillsides and river corridors. However, it is not yet clear to what extent this de-
 pends on the lateral flow in the subsurface although the resolved overland flow in ParFlow
 is a direct consequence of groundwater outcropping at the land surface, e.g., in the con-
 vergence zones of river valleys. In order to determine the relevance of lateral subsurface
 flow in this context, a sensitivity study with deactivated lateral exchange has been per-
 formed meaning that subsurface water is only allowed to flow vertically within the soil
 column. This requires an adaption of the lower boundary condition to free drainage mim-
 icking the hydrological parametrization in ICON-Land. Figure 5 shows the result of the
 sensitivity run (ICON-PFL-1D) compared to the default setup (ICON-PFL). Plotted is
 the lifting condensation level (LCL) in pressure levels calculated according to Georgakakos

Figure 5. Calculated lifting condensation level (LCL) in pressure levels averaged over the extended summer period of 2004. Grid points with a non-significant difference between ICON-PFL and ICON-PFL-1D are masked out.

and Bras (1984):

$$P_{lcl} = P_s \left(\frac{T_{2m} - T_{d,2m}}{223.15} + 1 \right)^{-3.5}$$

472 The LCL combines several near-surface quantities characterizing the atmospheric state,
 473 namely the 2 m temperature T_{2m} , the 2 m dew-point temperature $T_{d,2m}$, and the surface
 474 pressure P_s , into one variable, and is directly relevant for cloud formation. Grid points
 475 with a non-significant difference between ICON-PFL and ICON-PFL-1D are masked out.
 476 The significance testing is based on local t -tests followed by a p -value correction (FDR
 477 test, Wilks, 2016). As can be seen from the comparison of the unmasked areas in Figure
 478 5a and b, lateral groundwater flow corresponds to an increase in horizontal heterogeneity
 479 in the ICON-PFL simulation compared to the ICON-PFL-1D simulation. This
 480 is mainly due to a more heterogeneous soil moisture distribution that, consequently, alters
 481 surface air temperature and humidity. A dominant region with a significant impact
 482 of lateral groundwater flow is the Pannonian Basin in southeast Central Europe, which
 483 is surrounded by mountain ranges such as the Carpathian Mountains to north and east.
 484 Furthermore, this region showed strong land-atmosphere coupling in Figure 4. Note that
 485 ICON-PFL-1D was initialized with the same three-dimensional groundwater configuration
 486 as the default simulation. Due to unresolved convection, local effects are likely to
 487 be underestimated as well. With that, it can be stated that the lateral flow of near-surface
 488 groundwater will have a measurable impact on the evolution of the atmosphere. With-
 489 out the soil columns being connected laterally, the groundwater level does not evolve with
 490 respect to the topography and the river network is not able to develop accordingly.

491 4 Comparison to ERA5 Data

492 In the final section, the change in soil water content during the summer months
 493 in both the ICON-REF and ICON-PFL simulations is compared to ERA5 reanalysis data
 494 (Hersbach et al., 2020). With stronger land-atmosphere coupling in the ICON-PFL sim-
 495 ulations, soil water storage responds more directly to atmospheric processes. On the other
 496 hand, the ParFlow coupling is found to reduce the soil water variability in the deeper
 497 soil layers due to the formation of a fully saturated zone. In order to evaluate whether
 498 the change in soil water content in the upper soil layers over the summer months is ac-
 499 tually more realistic in the ICON-PFL simulations, it is averaged over a large area
 500 and compared to the relative change in averaged soil water content obtained from ERA5 data.
 501 A focus region inside the ParFlow computational domain (75% of the longitudinal and

Figure 6. Relative change in soil water content up to different soil depths from beginning to end of summer in an ensemble of the years 2002 to 2006 (a) averaged over the core ParFlow domain as shown by the dashed border (b). The error bars denote the standard deviation within the multi-year ensemble.

latitudinal extent) was selected as the area of interest. Therefore, the analysis is more representative for Central Europe, where precipitation is determined by large-scale weather systems such as Atlantic lows. The Arctic regions are excluded, as errors related to snow cover and the representation of soil ice are expected here. Figure 6a shows the decrease in soil water content in the upper soil layers during the summer season (JJA) relative to the beginning of summer. It is averaged over the multi-year ensemble (2002 to 2006). Compared to the ICON-REF simulations, a stronger overall reduction in soil moisture during the summer months is found in the ICON-PFL simulations. However, this varies between the different years, as can be seen from the standard deviation, which is slightly higher in the ERA5 data. The lower variability in the simulations is probably a consequence of unresolved meso-scale convection with the coarser resolution; thus, more rain falls in form of large-scale precipitation instead of stronger and more localized convective precipitation (see, e.g., Prein et al., 2015; Schär et al., 2020). Averaged over the upper 1 m of soil, the decrease in ICON-PFL is less pronounced. While still higher than in ICON-REF, the decrease in ERA5 is more than twice as high. However, in large areas such as Central Europe, the ICON-ParFlow coupling leads to seasonal soil water changes that are in a more realistic range.

5 Conclusion

This study shows that a coupling between a global atmospheric/land-surface model (ICON and ICON-Land) and a continental-scale hydrological model for shallow groundwater (ParFlow on the European CORDEX domain) limited to the exchange of liquid water leads to improved physical representation and additional insights. ParFlow is able to simulate a continuous, dynamic water table and a hydrologically heterogeneous land surface with continuously wet river basins and frequently drying water divides. This is found to have a significant impact on land-atmosphere coupling. With lateral flow, soil moisture evolves depending on the topography and the river network develops accordingly. Moreover, the formation of a river network in combination with three-dimensional groundwater flow exerts a direct feedback on the atmosphere. In areas, where a shortage of moisture is induced due to a physics-based implementation of runoff and infiltration, the feedback on temperature leads to further drying. As a result, with stronger land-atmosphere coupling, soil water content evolves in a feedback loop with lower atmospheric conditions. Already over the relatively short simulation period of a few months - in this case, the extended summer season - this would have strong implications on, e.g., weather regimes such as heat waves, or regional water resources. At first glance, the stronger decrease in soil moisture in parts of Europe during the summer months may seem to contradict the results of Barlage et al. (2021) and Colin et al. (2023) where the introduc-

538 tion of groundwater was associated with increased evapotranspiration and precipitation
 539 as well as reduced surface temperatures. However, our study is not a direct comparison
 540 of two versions of the same model with and without a representation of groundwater,
 541 but rather a comparison of two model concepts. Thus, it focuses on the additional fea-
 542 tures of a more physics-based hydrological model and their implications for large-scale,
 543 long-range projections. Due to the global setup, any soil water evaporated into the at-
 544 mosphere can be redistributed globally. Moreover, the feedback from regional hydrology
 545 to large-scale circulation patterns will affect the evolution of weather and climate
 546 on the global scale, which can be studied with the proposed model configuration. This
 547 opens new avenues for climate research, in particular with regard to seasonal forecast-
 548 ing and other long-range predictions. For future research, it should be investigated how
 549 an increase in model resolution to adequately resolve convection, as well as the treatment
 550 of snow and ground ice as part of the coupling, would improve the simulation results.

551 Open Research Section

552 The ICON (Icosahedral Nonhydrostatic) model is available at [https://gitlab.dkrz](https://gitlab.dkrz.de/icon/icon-model)
 553 [.de/icon/icon-model](https://gitlab.dkrz.de/icon/icon-mpim/-/tree/feature-parflow-coupling?ref_type=heads). The version used in this study is available at [https://gitlab](https://gitlab.dkrz.de/icon/icon-mpim/-/tree/feature-parflow-coupling?ref_type=heads)
 554 [.dkrz.de/icon/icon-mpim/-/tree/feature-parflow-coupling?ref_type=heads](https://gitlab.dkrz.de/icon/icon-mpim/-/tree/feature-parflow-coupling?ref_type=heads). ParFlow
 555 is available on GitHub. The version used in this study is located at [https://icg4geo](https://icg4geo.icg.kfa-juelich.de/ModelSystems/warmworld_parflow)
 556 [.icg.kfa-juelich.de/ModelSystems/warmworld_parflow](https://icg4geo.icg.kfa-juelich.de/ModelSystems/warmworld_parflow). The post-processed model
 557 output data and the scripts for creating the figures for this manuscript can be found at
 558 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14982047> (Weinkaemmerer et al., 2025).

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Figure 1.

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Figure 2.

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Figure 3.

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Figure 4.

Figure 5.

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LCL, ICON-PFL [hPa]

LCL, ICON-PFL-1D [hPa]

Figure 6.

